

BASIC OF LEARNING THEORY (BEHAVIORISM, COGNITIVISM, CONSTRUCTIVISM, AND HUMANISM)

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ABSTRACT

In general, the term learning is understood as the teacher's conscious effort to help students so that they can learn according to their interests and needs. The more aware and professional a teacher is in educating, the better the quality of students and vice versa. Another term that is combined with learning in this article is theory. In a general sense, the method is often associated with a set of concepts, ideas, and procedures that can be learned, analyzed, and verified. So, learning theory is a collection of thoughts, ideas, systems in which how to practice the learning process between teacher and student and other elements related to learning activities. Learning theory itself can be interpreted as a theory that contains procedures for how a teacher applies teaching and learning activities, which will later be used to students both inside and outside the classroom.

Keywords: *basic of learning, behaviorism, cognitivism, constructivism, humanism*

INTRODUCTION

Learning theory is an attempt to describe how humans learn, thus helping us all understand the complexities inherent process of learning. There are three main perspectives in learning theory, namely Behaviorism, Cognitivism, and Constructivism. The first theory is complemented by the second theory and so on, so that there are variants, main ideas, or figures that cannot be included, including which ones, or even become separate theories. But we don't need to debate this. What is essential for us to understand is which opinions are useful for specific regions, and which approaches are suitable for other areas. This kind of understanding is critical to be able to improve the quality of learning.

Learning theory pays attention to how a person influences other people to make the learning process. Bruner in Degeng (1989) suggests that learning theory is prescriptive, while learning theory is descriptive. Authoritarian means, the purpose of learning theory is to determine the appropriate learning method/strategy to obtain optimal results. In other words, the learning theory deals with efforts to control specific variables in learning theory to facilitate learning. While descriptive means, the purpose of learning theory is to explain the learning process. Learning theory pays attention to how a person learns.

For more details about learning theories, I will describe several approaches that will be used in the learning process.

UNDERSTANDING LEARNING THEORY

In general, the term learning is understood as the teacher's conscious effort to help students so that they can learn according to their interests and needs. The more aware and professional a teacher is in educating, the better the quality of students and vice versa.

Another term that is combined with learning in this article is theory. In a general sense, the method is often associated with a set of concepts, ideas, and procedures that can be learned, analyzed, and verified. So, learning theory is a collection of thoughts, ideas, systems in which how to practice the learning process between teacher and student and other elements related to learning activities. Learning theory itself can be interpreted as a theory that contains procedures for how a teacher applies teaching and learning activities, which will later be used to students both inside and outside the classroom.

1. Behaviorism

Behaviorism is a school of psychology that views individuals only in terms of physical phenomena and ignores mental aspects. In other words, behaviorism does not recognize the intelligence, talents, interests, and feelings of individuals in a study. Learning events train reflexes in such a way that they become habits that are mastered by individuals. In the Psychology Dictionary, several definitions of behaviorism are mentioned:

- a. The views of some psychologists in the early 20th century who opposed the method of introspection; and recommends that psychology be limited to the study of visible behavior (observable behavior) as a basis for consideration of scientific data.
- b. A flow system of psychology developed by John B. Watson. A general view that emphasizes the role of observable behavior (overt behavior) and reduces the meaning of mental processes.
- c. The view that states that human and animal behavior can be understood, bias can be predicted and controlled without the help of information relating to his mental state. A flow of psychology, which emphasizes that psychology is limited to the study of behavior.

Behaviorism is a school of psychology founded by John B. Watson in 1913 who argues that behavior must be a single subject of psychology. Behaviorism is a revolutionary school, persuasive and influential, and has deep historical roots. Behaviorism was born as a reaction to introspection (which analyzes the human soul based on subjective reports) and also Psychoanalysis (which talks about the invisible subconscious). The theory of learning behaviorism psychology was advanced by behavioristic psychologists. They believe that human behavior is controlled by rewards or reinforcement from the environment. Thus in the practice of learning, there is a close relationship between behavioral reactions with stimulation.

2. Cognitivism

Cognitive psychology is a branch of general psychology. It includes scientific studies of the symptoms of mental life insofar as it relates to the way humans think in gaining knowledge, processing impressions that enter through the senses, solving problems, digging up memories of expertise and work procedures needed in everyday life. Mental life encompasses cognitive, affective, conative symptoms to some degree, namely psychosomatics that cannot be separated from each other. Therefore, cognitive psychology not only explores the basis of typical cognitive symptoms but also from the affective (interpretation and consideration that accompanies the reaction of feelings), conative (will decisions).

Some experts have not been satisfied with the findings of previous experts about learning as a stimulus-response-reinforcement process. They argue that a person's behavior is not only controlled by reward and reinforcement. These are cognitive flow psychologists. In their opinion, a person's behavior is always based on cognition, which is the act of knowing or thinking about the situation in which the action occurs. In a learning situation, a person is directly involved in the position and gains insight for problem-solving. Thus, cognitivism holds that a person's behavior is more dependent on insight into the relationships that exist in a situation. The whole is more than its parts. They put pressure on the organization of

observations for stimuli in the environment as well as on the factors that influence consideration. Cognitive flow characteristics are:

- a. Increase what is in man
- b. Increase overall than parts
- c. Increasing the role of cognitive
- d. Improve current time conditions
- e. Increase the formation of cognitive structures
- f. Prioritizing balance in humans
- g. Prioritizing "insight" (understanding).

Characters include Kohler, Max Wertheimer, Kurt Lewin, and Bandura. Their learning theory was created based on the experiments of each, which is not the same. Still, the basis of their learning is the same, namely that in education, there is the ability to measure the environment, so the situation does not automatically affect humans.

3. Constructivism

Constructivism is the development of Cognitive learning theory. Constructivism departs from the belief that knowledge is a process of formation that continues to develop and change. Education is always a result of the cognitive construction of reality through one's activities. Experience is not guaranteed or fixed but rather a process of becoming know. The essence of constructivism theory is the idea that students must find and transform complex information into other situations, and if desired, that information becomes their own. With this basis, learning must be packaged into a process of constructing rather than receiving knowledge. The foundation of constructivism thinking is somewhat different from the view of objectivity, which places more emphasis on learning outcomes. In the perspective of constructivism, the strategy of gaining precedence over how much students acquire and remember knowledge. For this reason, the teacher's job is to facilitate the process by:

- a. Making learning meaningful and relevant for students;
- b. Allow students to find and implement their ideas;
- c. They were making students aware of their strategies for learning.

Based on the above understanding it can be concluded that constructivism is a view based on the acquisition of knowledge or construction (formation) of people who are learning that begins with the occurrence of cognitive conflict which at the end of the learning process of knowledge will be built by through experience from the results of interaction with the environment. Constructivism Learning is one view of the learning process, which states that the learning process (acquisition of knowledge) begins with the occurrence of cognitive conflict. This cognitive conflict can only be overcome through education that will be built himself through his experience of the results of interactions with his environment. Karli further said that:

Cognitive conflict occurs when the interaction between the initial conceptions that have been owned by students with new phenomena can be integrated just like that so that changes in cognitive structure modifications are needed to achieve balance, this event will occur continuously, as long as students receive new knowledge

Constructivism can be done by giving problems to students. The provision of questions is intended to stimulate students to think and think critically when they are confronted with new facts. Students are treated as thinkers or trained to be thinkers, not just as passive recipients of knowledge—constructivist learning places more emphasis on learning process skills, not solely on learning outcomes. To achieve learning goals, the strategy the teacher undertakes is to create collaborative learning, which allows discussion of a problem from various points of view. The acquisition of student knowledge begins with the adoption of new

things as a result of interaction with the environment; then, these new things are compared with the initial conception that has been previously owned. The teacher acts more as a facilitator and mediator of learning. The emphasis on learning and teaching focuses more on the success of students in organizing their experiences. The importance is on the students who are learning and not on the discipline or the teacher who is teaching. The function of the teacher as a mediator and facilitator can be described in the following tasks:

- a. Providing learning experiences that enable students to be responsible for making designs, processes, and research, therefore, clearly giving lectures or lectures is not the main task of a teacher or lecturer.
- b. Provide or provide activities that stimulate students' curiosity and help them to express their ideas and communicate their scientific ideas.
- c. Monitor, evaluate, and show whether students' thinking is working or not. The teacher teaches and questions whether the student's knowledge applies to deal with new related problems. The teacher helps evaluate students' hypotheses and conclusions.

According to Siraj, the characteristics of constructivist learning are: 1) Provide learning experiences by linking the knowledge that students have in such a way that is learning through the process of knowledge formation; 2) Providing various alternative learning experiences, not all do the same task, for example, a problem can be solved in multiple ways; 3) Integrating learning with realistic and relevant situations involving concrete experiences, for example, to understand a concept through the reality of everyday life; 4) Integrating learning to enable social transmission that is the occurrence of interaction and cooperation of a person with others or with the environment, for example, interaction and collaboration between students, teachers, and students; 5) Utilizing various media including oral and written communication so that learning becomes more active; 6) Involving students emotionally and socially so that it becomes exciting and students want to learn.

Broadly speaking, the principles of constructivism taken are knowledge built students themselves, both personally and socially. Active students construct continuous so that there is a change in the concept of concepts that are more detailed, complete. In accordance with scientific ideas, knowledge is not transferred from teacher to student, except with the activeness of students themselves to reason, the teacher's role is to help provide facilities and situations. Hence, the construction process of students runs smoothly—the leaders of the schools of Constructivism Tasker, Wheatley, Hudoyo, Hanbury, and Tyler.

4. Humanism

The third type of theory is the humanistic theory. Humanism is the flow of humanity. Humanism is a psychological approach, which emphasizes human problems, interests, values, and human dignity. According to the psychology dictionary, there are several notions of Humanistic psychology including 1) An approach to psychology that emphasizes trying to see people as whole beings, by focusing on subjective awareness, researching critical human problems, and enriching human life; 2) Psychological approach in general, which emphasizes the particular characteristics that distinguish human beings from other animals. Humanistic psychologists especially emphasize sociative and productive human capacities; 3) The approach to the study of human existence, which underscores the problem for the whole person and the essential elements (constituents) of the internal and integrative of one's personal totality, motives, intentions, feelings, feelings and so on.

For adherents of this theory, the learning process must originate and lead to humans themselves. Of the four learning methods, this humanistic theory is the most abstract, the closest to the philosophical world than the world of education. Although this theory strongly emphasizes the importance of the "content" of the learning process, in reality, this theory is

more about teaching and learning in its most ideal form. In other words, this theory is more interested in the idea of learning in its most perfect way than learning as it is, like what we usually observe in the everyday world. Naturally, if this theory is very eclectic, any method can be utilized as long as the goal is to humanize humans (achieve self-actualization and so on) can be made. In the world of education, the flow of humanism emerged in the 1960s to the 1970s, and perhaps the changes and innovations that occurred during the last two decades of the 20th century will also go in this direction. (John Jarolimak and Clifford Foster, 1976, p.330). In highlighting behavioral problems, behavioral and humanistic psychologists have very different views. This difference is known as the freedom determination issue.

Behaviorists view people as reactive beings who respond to their environment. Experience and maintenance will shape their behavior. Instead, humanists have the opinion that each person determines their practice. They are free in choosing the quality of their lives, not bound by their friends. Cognitive Psychology was perfected by figures such as Carl Rogers and Frankle. So cognitive characteristics are still found in the flow of humanism psychology. The aspects of the flow of humanism: Concern with humans as individuals; Concern about personal unanimity; Concerned about the role of cognitive and practical; Concerned with the subjective perceptions that each individual has; Concerned about the ability to determine the form of one's behavior; Prioritizing "insight."

Abraham Maslow (1908-1970) can be seen as the father of humanistic psychology. This movement is a psychological movement that is dissatisfied with behavioristic psychology and psychoanalysis and looks for alternative psychology that focuses on humans with the characteristics of its existence. This movement came to be known as humanistic psychology (Misiak and Sexton, 1988). Humans are creative beings, controlled not by the forces of the unconscious-psychoanalysis-but by their values and choices. In 1958 Maslow named humanistic psychology a "third force," besides behavioristic psychology and psychoanalysis as the first and second forces. There are four characteristics of psychology that are humanistic oriented, namely: 1) Focusing on the person experiencing, and therefore focusing on the experience as a primary phenomenon in studying humans; 2) Emphasizing distinctive qualities such as creativity, self-actualization, as opposed to mechanical and reductionistic human thought; 3) Relying on meaningfulness in choosing problems to be studied and research procedures to be used. Give full attention and place the highest value on human dignity and dignity and are interested in the development of potential inherent in each individual (Misiak and Sexton, 1988). Aside from Maslow as a figure in humanistic psychology, Carl Rogers (1902-1987) is famous for being client-centered therapy.

CONCLUSION

Based on the previous description, it can be concluded as follows: Behaviorism is a school of psychology founded by John B. Watson in 1913 who argued that behavior must be the sole subject of psychology. Behaviorism is a revolutionary school, persuasive and influential, and has a relatively deep historical root. Characteristics of Behaviorism: 1) Concerned with environmental influences; 2) Concern over parts of the whole; 3) Concerned with psychomotor reactions; 4) Concerning the causes of the past; 5) Concerned about forming habits; 6) Prioritizing the mechanism of learning outcomes; 7) Prioritizing "trial and error." Behaviorism flow figures include; E.L. Thorndike, Ivan Petrovich Pavlov, B.F. Skinner, and Bandura.

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up memories of expertise and work procedures needed in everyday life. Cognitive flow characteristics are: 1) Increase what is in man; 2) Increase overall than parts; 3) Increase the cognitive role; 4) Improve current time conditions; 5) Increase the formation of cognitive structures; 6) Prioritizing balance in humans; 7) Prioritizing "insight" (understanding); c. Cognitive flow figures include Kohler, Max Wertheimer, Kurt Lewin, and Bandura.

Constructivism Learning is one of the views about the learning process, which states that the learning process (acquisition of knowledge) begins with the occurrence of cognitive conflict. This cognitive conflict can only be overcome through education that will be built the child himself through his experience of the results of interactions with his environment. The characteristics of constructivist learning are: 1) Providing learning experiences by linking the knowledge that students already have in such a way that was learning through the process of knowledge formation; 2) Various alternative learning experiences, not all do the same task, for example, a problem can be solved in multiple ways; 3) Integrate learning with realistic and relevant situations by involving concrete experiences, for example, to understand a concept through the reality of everyday life; 4) Integrating learning to enable social transmission, that is, the interaction and cooperation of a person with others or with the environment, for example, interaction and collaboration between students, teachers, and students; 5) Make use of various media including oral and written communication so that learning becomes more active; 6) Involving students emotionally and socially so that it becomes exciting and students want to learn. Constructivism flow figures include; Tasker, Wheatley, Hudoyo, Hanbury, and Tytler.

Humanism is a psychological approach, which highlights human problems, interests, values, and human dignity. The characteristics of the flow of humanism: 1) Concern with humans as individuals; 2) Concern on personal roundness; 3) Concerned with the role of cognitive and practical; 4) Concerned with the subjective perceptions that each individual has; 5) Concerned about the ability to determine the form of one's behavior; 6) Prioritize "insight." Psychology of Humanism such characters as Carl Rogers and Frankle. Abraham Maslow (1908-1970) can be seen as the father of humanistic psychology.

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